

“The study of SEO for organic branding of SMEs.”

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ABSTRACT

The search engine information transfer accurately & efficiently and do this website optimization to improve the web search result ranking on SERP Starting with understanding the Algorithms of the search engine. This research paper exports the specific explanation of Search Engine Optimisations for organic branding.

Search Engine Optimisations is a process that uses can search principles for search engines to provide a top ranking to the more suitable webpage on SERP.

This research paper aims to cover all SEO methods for optimizing the website for the search engine, necessary for SME's Website, effective Organic Ranking. Analysis of the SME's valid Organic website promotion.

1. INTRODUCTION

SEO helps SMEs to manage user-friendly, fast, and websites that rank TOP in (SERP) Search Engines Result Page, which in turn improves more qualified potential users to their websites and ultimately increases the organic lead conversion rates.

SEO helps build organic brand awareness for SMEs as search engine users are more likely to trust a website that is on the first page of SERP's than brands who are not. SEO is probably the most effective, natural, and affordable marketing strategy that exists today. Furthermore, it will merely bring in customers who are actively looking to find services and products.

Actually, there are many SEO roles for SMEs and Startup businesses in the digital era. The most obvious benefit of SEO for SMEs is potential traffic that comes from search engines. One of the main advantages of getting top rankings on the SERPs. SEO can build organic brand awareness for SMEs.

For small and medium-sized enterprises Website, the primary Search engine optimization areas to consider the following points.

- **Website.** A mobile-AMP friendly fast-loading, well-structured, site is crucial.
- **Content.** Organic content can help prove why a user should choose you.
- **Content marketing.** Informational blog content can put in front of a wider audience.
- **On Site-page SEO.** Basic optimization is essential, so think page meta descriptions and titles.
- **Local SEO.** Local businesses and SMEs also need to be considered local SEO, most effective practices.
- **Website Authority building.** Links are still highly corresponded with reliable SERP results.
- **Credibility.** Portfolios, Case studies testimonials, and reviews help close the deal.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] M. Singh and S. Kumar P. Chahal "Ranking of Website Reports ."

This paper proposed

a novel technique that makes the user also search for data quite efficient. This technique gives similarity and a relationship between the searched document and user search query. It is also considered the semantic structure of the document and user search query.

[2] G. S. Bedi,(March 2014), shows the importance of some techniques of SEO,

He described previous work done on the subject of Search engine optimization, the early beginning of SEO, its goals and ideas such as Black Hat SEO, White Hat SEO, Off-Page, On-page SEO, their benefits.

[3] Joeran Beel, discussed the concept of academic SEO.

Based on three recently conducted studies, guidelines are provided on how to optimize scholarly literature for academic search engines in general and Google Scholar in particular. Also, he briefly discussed the risk of researchers' illegitimately 'over-optimizing' their articles.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To study Website content management and Keywords Optimization.
- To study Brand or Product related key words analysis.
- To study the impact of the promotional strategy of SEO for SMEs.
- To study of generating organic traffic.
- To study of increase organic leads.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodology has been used in this research study.

Research Type :

Descriptive Research:

This analysis work is a kind of descriptive study that involves analyzing and evaluating existing knowledge and practices in the field of website organic promotion. We focus on the area of Website Organic Genuine Content and search engine Algorithms.

Project Study is simply the process of probing questions and answering them by experiment or survey in a structured way. It is also a procedure of systematic collection, analysis, and understanding of data to answer a

particular query and solving a Query.

This research on the topic "**To STUDY OF SEO FOR ORGANIC BRANDING OF SMEs**" to analyze whether SEO for a particular business website can be valuable to rank it the higher top position in the SERP and enhance the Organic Ranking and maximize organic leads.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Here are some questions:

Q1. Is SEO a useful tool for Internet marketing?

Q2. Is SEO Useful for Website Ranking?

Q3. Is it relevant for SMEs to perform SEO?

5. COLLECTION OF DATA

❑ Data refers to facts or information

- It includes descriptive effects on quantitative and qualitative information numerical information.
- The collection of research data is a crucial stage in research. The quality of data determines the quantity of data research.

❑ Primary data collection:

- Gathered through in-depth conversations, electronic surveys, or a series of informal discussions.

❑ Collection of Secondary data :

- Secondary data collection are the data that have already collected for purposes other than the research query at hand

6. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. SEARCH ENGINE
2. KEYWORDS FOR SEARCH
3. SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION

4. On PAGE SEO
5. OFF-PAGE SEO
6. TECHNICAL SEO

1. SEARCH ENGINE

An SEO is a web-based tool that allows users to find information on the (WWW) World Wide Web(Search Engine). Great examples of search engines are Yahoo!, Google, MSN, Baidu, Bing A SK Search engines, DuckDuckGo, use automated as robots, bots, or spiders that travel along the Web, following links from page to page, the website to website. The data gathered by the Crawler and spider is used to create a searchable index of the Web.

There are so several search engines in the market, but in all that Google (www.google.com) is in a high position with the other two main opponents, Microsoft's Bing search engine (www.bing.com) and yahoo (www.yahoo.com). The market share for the top search engines presented in the following chart.

2.KEYWORDS FORSEARCH

Keyword research is a big part of SEO. To do a lot of the other things on this list effectively analyzed keywords, you need first to have a clear idea of the main terms and subject areas or targeted audience focus SEO efforts on.

Keyword analysis. From further nomination, identify a targeted list of phrases and long-tail keywords Review competitive records and other pertinent industry sources. Use your preliminary list to determine an indicative number of recent SERP queries and how many websites are competing for every key word. Prioritize keywords and plurals, phrases singulars, and misspellings.

Keyword Research Tools:- Google Key word Research, Moz, Semrush, etc....

Best keyword research tools

Tool	Keyword suggestions	Data filtering	Search volume trend	Keyword difficulty	SERP analysis
	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★
	★★★☆☆	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★
	★★★☆☆	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★☆☆
	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★☆☆☆☆	★☆☆☆☆
	★★★★★	★★★☆☆	★★★★★	---	★★★☆☆
	★★★☆☆	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★	★★★★★

ahrefs

3. SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION

SEO stands for search engine optimization, is the process of improving the visibility of an optimized website with increasing the quantity and quality of traffic within the organic search engine results. Fulfilled, in part, through technical fixes, and content creation and enhancements, SEO is as much art as it is science.

4. **On PAGE SEO**

In On-page SEO, providing Genuine content for target audience based keywords selection, putting keywords on correct places, giving appropriate meta title and meta description to every page.

Example:- 1. Including website key word in the title tag.

2. Meta descriptions Optimizations with key words

3. URLs Optimizations

4. Heading tags optimizations with key words.

5. Optimize images

6. What Google Search Console

7. Website submit in Google search console

8. What is XML Sitemaps?

9. Create an XML sitemap and HTML Sitemap and submit to Webmaster.

10. Xml sitemap Submit in Google search console.

11. What is robots.txt?

12. Robots.txt file submit in Google search console and cPanel

13. Setup Google Analytics Tracking to a Website.

5. **OFF-PAGE SEO**

Creating High DA PA Backlink from website

• Using the most crucial Off-page SEO Activities for building website backlinks

• Article Submission, PPT Submissions, Search Engine Submission,

• Answer Questions, PDF Submissions

• Directory Submission, Social Bookmarking

Benefits of SEO:

We can summarize some significant benefits and advantages of SEO as follows:

- 1) The primary advantage of SEO covering any other type of Internet marketing is that you can be ranked keyword on top 10 SERP positions.
- 2) In the long term, the significant advantages of SEO over paid advertising are ROI. The company website will indeed take some time to get ranked for an organic keyword, and once ranked, the return-on-investment (ROI) becomes excellent as you get a lot of free traffic for your website.
- 3) The site is obtainable for an oversized range of on-line customers in an exceedingly very convenient approach. A better-optimized web site attracts additional guests and potential leads.

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Q2 Where to check website traffic and Leads

Using google analytics tool.

Q3. After SEO Optimizations.What if Significant growth in business?

Increased the potential leads and Customer

Increased website traffic

Increased website Organic Search

Local SEO has been Increased Engagement, Traffic & Conversions.

7.FINDINGS

- Attractive Custom Design Layout
- You can add, edit update, any content in the website through easy to use admin panel
- Keywords Research.
- Keywords Optimizations.
- Create a High PR backlinks.
- Responsive (Mobile Friendly) Design Theme.
- SEO Tool for higher top ranking in SERP.
- Monthly website traffic Analytical Report
- Monthly Ranking Analysis
- Accessible and Secure to Use Interface & Backend
- Advertisement Management

8. SUGGESTIONS :

- Identify a unique key word and content for search engine optimization.
- Creating and publishing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and acquire a clearly defined audience.
- Speed optimization.
- Image Alt Tag Optimizations.
- Website On-Page Title and Description Optimizations.
- Lead Management.
- Website Traffic Analysis.

9. CONCLUSION:

- It helps the business to have an organically global reach.
- Online presence is crucial for every day SME's businesses, and an SEO strategy can help make you stand out above your competitors on the SERP.
- It helps to track Website Traffic and measure the reach for your product/services.
- It helps your business to get engaged with the Targeted Customer.

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